

Organo-antimony Compounds. Part V. Preparation of some Substituted Benzyl Benzoates and their Antimony Derivatives.

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In a recent paper, Gough and King (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, p. 669) has discussed the relationship between the chemical constitution of a series of compounds starting from benzamide-*p*-arsinic acid and their trypanocidal activity, on *Trypanosoma equiperdum* in rats. The conclusions which the above authors have arrived at are very interesting. It has been demonstrated that benz-*m*- and -*p*-arsinic acids, hippuro-*p*-arsinic acid, salicylic acid-5-arsinic acid, *p*-sulphophenylarsinic acid, as also the corresponding arsinous acids, are inactive against experimental trypanosomiasis in mice, but when these are converted into their corresponding amides, trypanocidal activity appears in every case. The inactivity of the first series of arsenicals has been explained by assuming that so long as the compounds contain the free carboxyl or sulpho-group, they are capable of forming soluble salts and of being rapidly excreted from the system, whether the arsenic is present in the tri- or penta-valent condition. On the other hand, the amides are also excreted, though probably at a slower rate, so long as the arsinic acid group remains intact, and they are capable of forming soluble salts. When, however, the pentavalent arsinic acid has been reduced to the trivalent arsinous stage, they will no longer be capable of forming soluble salts, but they will then be liberated in the colloidal state and consequently will not be excreted rapidly. The conversion of pentavalent arsinic acids to the trivalent arsinous acids is supposed to take place through the action of thiol-derivatives, in tissues. The excess of thiol groups then combines with arsinous acids thus produced, forming arylthioarsinites (*cf.* Ehrlich. *Ber.*, 1909, 42, 42; Voegtalin, *Physiol. Rev.*, 1925, 5, 63). The continuous and gradual hydrolysis of the arylthioarsinites would lead to the production of small quantities of highly toxic arsinous acids and this process maintained for a considerable time would be responsible for the disappearance of the trypanosomes with resultant cure.

But there is one consideration which goes seriously against this elaborate theory of trypanocidal action. It has been observed in the routine test of arseno-compounds, that even after the first application of the drug in rats, infected with *Trypanosome equiperdum*, the number of trypanosomes per c.c. diminish very rapidly, within twenty-four hours. It is not possible to assume that the elaborate operations discussed above, would be complete within this short time and the theory of Gough and King cannot therefore be accepted as it stands. Another experimental fact which goes against this amide theory is the entire lack of activity of a number of stibinic acids prepared from benzyl *o*-, *m*-, and *p*-aminobenzoates (Niyogy, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 7, 577). If it is assumed that the only influence of the amide group is to depress the tendency of formation of soluble salts, it is strange that these stibinic acids, in which the carboxyl group is protected by a benzyl group and in consequence, incapable of forming salts, should exhibit no trypanocidal activity. From this it must be admitted that amide formation not only prevents the formation of soluble salts but also brings about some fundamental difference in the nature of the compounds. The inefficiency of the stibinic acids mentioned above might be due, as suggested by Gough and King (*loc. cit.*) to any of the following causes: (i) the esterification of carboxyl group probably removes the stibinic acid from the range of the reduction potential of the tissues and thus they remain in the pentavalent form which is rapidly removed from the system; (ii) the ester may not combine so very easily with thiol complexes, as the amide; (iii) the hydrolysis of the arylthiostibinites may not proceed so easily as with amides.

Among the antimonials which have been prepared thus far, it has been found that only the aminophenylstibinic acid and some of its derivatives are active against infections caused by Leishman-Donovan bodies. Of the three isomers, the *para*-compound has been studied more systematically than the others and appears to possess a therapeutic index sufficiently high to be employed in practice. Now according to the theory of trypanocidal activity put forward by Gough and King, the *para*-compound may fulfil the conditions laid down in the previous paragraph while the isomeric benzyl esters mentioned before do not conform to them and are consequently of no therapeutic value. Assuming, therefore, that for the production of an active trypanocide, an amino-group must be present in *para*-position to the stibinic acid residue, an attempt has been made to prepare benzyl

benzoate-2-aminophenyl-5-stibinic acid. The effect of elongating the acyl group which is employed for protecting the 2-amino-group was also considered to be of interest and has been one of the objects of the present communication. Moreover an attempt has also been made to prepare a compound of the type benzyl benzoate-2-acylamino-5-stibinic acid, so that the influence of the alkoxy group on the trypanocidal action, if any, may be studied further.

The starting materials are obviously 5-nitro-2-aminobenzoic acid and 5-nitro-2-aminobenzyl alcohol. In order to obtain both as the result of a single operation, the most suitable starting material is undoubtedly 5-nitro-2-acetylaminobenzaldehyde (Cohn and Springer, *Monatsh.*, 1903, **24**, 96). By the application of Cannizzaro's reaction 5-nitro-2-acetylaminobenzoic acid and 5-nitro-2-acetylaminobenzyl alcohol were expected ; but in practice, it was found that the acetyl group was knocked off in the course of the reaction and free amines were isolated. Both the acid and the alcohol were then re-acetylated with acetic anhydride.

The m.p. of 5-nitro-2-acetylaminobenzoic acid, prepared by the direct nitration of 2-acetylaminobenzoic acid, had been given by Rupe (*Ber.*, 1897, **30**, 1097) to be 152° while Ullmann and Uzbachian (*Ber.*, 1903, **36**, 1797) had obtained the same compound with m.p. 221°, by the oxidation of 5-nitro-2-acetylaminotoluene with calcium permanganate, the m.p. of the base, 5-nitro-2-aminobenzoic acid being 263°. In the present investigation the m.p. of 5-nitro-2-aminobenzoic acid prepared by Cannizzaro's reaction from the corresponding aldehyde was found to be 262-63° which on acetylation gave a product which melted at 216-17°. It would appear from these observations that the product obtained by Rupe (*loc. cit.*) was not the expected 5-nitro-compound. To settle this question, it was considered necessary to repeat the experiments of the previous authors. Careful repetition of Rupe's experiment showed that in some cases, the product had m.p. 152° while in a few cases, the m.p. was 217-18°. Although Ullmann and Uzbachian (*loc. cit.*) had worked with 5-nitro-2-acetylaminotoluene, yet no reference or details of its preparation had been given by the authors ; the literature (*Z. Chem.*, 1871, *ii*, 7, 99) contains a single reference to this compound. For the purpose of the present work, *o*-acetotoluidide was nitrated in sulphuric acid solution and the product was then oxidised with potassium permanganate and magnesium sulphate (compare D.R.P. 94629) to give a nitroacetylaminobenzoic acid

which after purification had m.p. 216-17°. This m.p. was not depressed when this product was mixed with a sample of 5-nitro-2-acetylaminobenzoic acid, prepared from the corresponding aldehyde. This operation not only enables one to correct the m.p. of 5-nitro-2-acetylaminobenzoic acid but also to establish the constitution of the nitration product of 2-acetylaminotoluene. Thus it appears that the m.p. of 5-nitro-2-acetylaminobenzoic acid is 216-17° as described by Ullmann and Uzbachian (*loc. cit.*). The product of m.p. 152° obtained by Rupe might have been a nitro-amino-compound of the following type, the nitro group subsequently migrating to position 5.

But unfortunately when attempts were made to bring about this conversion by warming the product of m.p. 152°, with dilute mineral acids, the acetyl group was knocked off and 5-nitro-2-aminobenzoic acid, m. p. 262-63°, was obtained in every case.

The next step was the preparation of the required esters, benzyl 5-nitro-2-acetylaminobenzoate and 5-nitro-2-acetylaminobenzyl benzoate. All common methods failed to give the ester of 5-nitro-2-acetylaminobenzoic acid with benzyl alcohol. By converting the carboxylic acid into the silver salt and heating this in benzene suspension with benzyl chloride, the ester was obtained. But up till now, all attempts to prepare 5-nitro-2-acetylaminobenzyl benzoate from the corresponding alcohol have been unsuccessful. A rather interesting observation was made when attempts were being made to prepare 5-nitro-2-acetylaminobenzyl benzoate. 5-Nitro-2-acetylaminotoluene on being treated with bromine in chloroform solution (with iodine as catalyst) (Brewster, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1918, **40**, 406) gave a bromo-compound which could not be crystallised. Assuming this to be 5-nitro-2-acetylaminobenzyl bromide, attempts were made to prepare the required ester by heating this in benzene solution with silver benzoate; a product was thus isolated (m.p. 143-44°) but the analytical data showed that it was not the ester but corresponded more closely with 5-nitro-2-acetylaminobenzyl alcohol, m.p. 157-58°. But the mixed m.p. of the alcohol and this product was below 140° and they therefore cannot be identical. On

repeatedly extracting the supposed benzyl bromide from water only (without heating with silver benzoate), the same product was isolated. It was found to be soluble in alkali and gave a coloration with ferric chloride, showing the presence of a phenolic hydroxy group. Thus it appears that the product might probably be 5-nitro-2-acetylamino-3-hydroxytoluene formed according to the following scheme :

In this scheme it is found that bromine atom wanders from the nitrogen atom to position 3, but the replacement of the nuclear halogen by simple boiling with water is rather unusual.

In order to ascertain the effect, if any, of elongating the acyl group, which is used to protect the amino-group, the following compounds were also prepared: benzyl 5-nitro-2-propionylaminobenzoate, benzyl 5-nitro-2-isobutyrylamino-benzoate, the starting point in each case being 2-aminobenzoic acid ; these were converted into the propionyl and isobutyryl derivatives by heating with the respective acid chlorides. The acetylated products were then nitrated and the nitro-compounds were converted into the corresponding silver salts and heated with benzyl chloride as described before. The reduction of the nitro-compounds to the corresponding amines were carried out by aluminium-mercury couple as described in a previous communication (Niyogy, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 7, 577); the only difference was that benzyl 5-nitro-2-acetylamino-benzoate was found to be very sparingly soluble in ether and so moist benzene was used as solvent. After the reducing operation, the bases were found to exhibit beautiful fluorescence. The stibinic acids were then prepared from these amines by the well-known diazo-reaction with careful regulation of temperature and quantity of alkali employed during the decomposition to prevent hydrolysis of the ester or the acyl group.

EXPERIMENTAL.

5-Nitro-2-acetylaminobenzoic Acid and 5-Nitro-2-acetylaminobenzyl Alcohol.—5-Nitro-2-acetylaminobenzaldehyde was prepared according to the method of Cohn and Springer (*loc. cit.*), the yield being 90 per cent. The nitroacetylaminobenzaldehyde (10 g.) was gradually added to a solution of caustic potash (5 g.) in water (30 c.c.) cooled in ice to 0° and vigorously shaken after each addition. It was found that the whole of the aldehyde did not go into solution but the light yellow colour of the nitroaldehyde deepened as the reaction proceeded (time of addition 2 hours.). The reaction flask was then allowed to stand overnight in a refrigerator and the yellow viscous mass was then diluted with water. It was then repeatedly extracted with ether, till almost the whole of the solid had gone into solution. The ethereal layer was next dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. On distilling off the ether, a yellow solid was obtained. Recrystallised from alcohol (twice) it had m. p. 197-98° (yield 80%). This product was found to be insoluble in alkali but fairly soluble in acids and to give diazo-reaction. It thus appears to be the free base and not the acetylated product. (Found: N, 17.02. $C_7H_8O_3N_2$ requires N, 16.66 per cent.).

The aqueous solution (after ether extraction) was acidified with hydrochloric acid when a light yellow solid separated. This was twice crystallised from dilute alcohol in long yellow needles, m. p. 267-68° (yield 75%). This product was found to be soluble in dilute sodium carbonate and to give diazo-reaction. It is therefore 5-nitro-2-aminobenzoic acid. (The m. p. of the acid as recorded by previous workers is 263-64°).

The *acetyl* derivative was prepared by heating the sample with acetic anhydride at 120-40° for 2 hours. It was crystallised from water as yellow needles, m. p. 216-17° (*cf.* Ullmann and Uzbachian, *loc. cit.*) (Found: N, 12.15. $C_9H_9O_5N_2$ requires N, 12.4 per cent.).

5-Nitro-2-acetylaminobenzyl Alcohol.—The required alcohol (4 g.) was heated at 140-50° for 2 hours with acetic anhydride (12 c.c.). On being poured into water an oily liquid separated which solidified after some time to a yellowish-brown mass. Recrystallised from alcohol it had m. p. 157-58°. (Found: N, 13.93. $C_9H_{10}O_4N_2$ requires N, 13.33 per cent.).

2-Acetylaminobenzoic Acid.—The methods which have been employed by the previous workers were not very convenient. Wheeler and Barnes (*Amer. Chem. J.*, 1898, **20**, 222) obtained

it by the action of acetyl chloride on the silver salt of aminobenzoic acid while Pawlewski (*Ber.*, 1898, **31**, 663) employed thioacetic acid and aminobenzoic acid. An easier and simpler method has now been found out.

o-Aminobenzoic acid (5 g.) was dissolved in acetic acid (20 c.c.). Acetic anhydride (10 c.c.) was then added when much heat was generated and a light brown crystalline solid immediately separated. On cooling, the solid was filtered off and washed with hot water till free from acid; m. p. 185-86° (yield 6 g.).

Nitration of 2-Acetylamino benzoic Acid (*cf.* Rupe, *Ber.*, 1897, **30**, 1097).—Acetylanthranilic acid (20 g.) was gradually added to sulphuric acid (60 c.c.) with gentle agitation, till the whole of the solid had gone into solution. The acid solution was then cooled in ice water and a mixture of nitric acid (8 g., *d* 1.40) and sulphuric acid (20 c.c.) was slowly added with stirring (time 1 hour); the stirring was continued for another 30 minutes. The acid liquid was then poured into crushed ice. A light yellow viscous mass separated which solidified after some time. This was filtered off and washed free from acid and recrystallised from water, m. p. 157-58° (yield 22 g.). The substance was found to dissolve easily in dilute sodium carbonate solution but did not give diazo reaction. It appears to be identical with the product obtained by Rupe (*loc. cit.*). But on repeating this experiment, the nitrated product was found to have m. p. 216-17° (*cf.* Ullmann and Uzbachian, *loc. cit.*)

5-Nitro-2-acetylamino toluene.—*o*-Acetotoluidide was gradually added to sulphuric acid (45 c.c.) cooled in ice, with mechanical stirring. After complete solution, a mixture of nitric acid (8 c.c., *d* 1.40) and concentrated sulphuric acid (15 c.c.) was slowly added. When the operation was concluded the acid solution was poured into crushed ice. A light pink coloured pasty mass separated which solidified after being allowed to stand for sometime. The solid was then filtered off, washed with water till free from acid and dried in *vacuo* over sulphuric acid. The product thus obtained (of a light pink colour) melted with decomposition at 101.4° (the m. p. of 5-nitro-2-acetylamino toluene, described by Beilstein and Kuhlberg, *Z. Chem.*, 1871, *ii*, **7**, 99, is 102-3°) when however the raw product was crystallised twice from dilute alcohol, it melted at 197-98°. (Found: N, 14.52. $C_9H_{10}O_3N_2$ requires N, 14.43 per cent.).

As the m. p. of the nitrated products obtained by Beilstein and Kuhlberg (*loc. cit.*) was found to be different from that obtained during the course of this work, the identity of my product (m. p. 197-98°) was established in the following way.

The nitro-compound (2 g.) was added to water (200 c.c.) followed by magnesium sulphate (5 g.) The liquid was then heated up to boiling with vigorous stirring till the greater part of the nitro-compound had gone into solution. To this was then added powdered potassium permanganate (6 g.) in small quantities at a time and the stirring continued for 2 hours. Excess of permanganate was then destroyed by adding alcohol to the hot liquid and filtered off from the precipitated manganese dioxide. The filtrate, when acidulated with dilute sulphuric acid, deposited pale yellow needles which after recrystallisation melted at 216-17°. The m.p. was not depressed when mixed with another sample of 5-nitro-2-acetylaminobenzoic acid. It was found to be soluble in dilute alkali and did not give diazo-reaction. On warming with alkali, the acetyl group was removed and a product separated which melted at 263-64°. Thus it appears that the m.p. of 5-nitro-2-acetylaminotoluene is 197-98° and not 101° as given by Beilstein and Kuhlberg (*loc. cit.*).

Bromination of 5-Nitro-2-acetylaminotoluene.—5-Nitro-2-acetylaminotoluene (2.5 g.) was dissolved in chloroform and a crystal of iodine was added. The solution was heated under reflux on a water-bath and bromine (0.8 c.c.) in chloroform (10 c.c.) was slowly added to the boiling solution. At first no evolution of hydrobromic acid was noticed but after about 2 hours, fumes of hydrobromic acid were given off. After 4 hours, heating the reaction mixture was left overnight. Excess of solvent was then distilled off when a yellow pasty solid was left. Attempts to purify this were unsuccessful. This was taken up in benzene and heated under reflux with silver benzoate (2.5 g.) for 2 hours. A solid was found to have separated which was filtered off and the filtrate was evaporated to dryness. A brown oil was left which solidified *in vacuo*. The brown solid was repeatedly extracted with water and filtered. The united filtrates were then boiled with animal charcoal and again filtered. The filtrate on cooling gave a yellow needle shaped crystalline precipitate, m.p. 135-37°. Recrystallised from water (charcoal) it melted at 141-42°. (Found: C, 51.74; H, 4.99; N, 13.72. $C_9H_{10}O_4N_2$ requires C, 51.4 ; H, 4.76; N, 13.33 per cent.).

In another experiment, the residue left after evaporation of chloroform was repeatedly washed with water and the product that was isolated had m.p. 141-42° and analytical results identical with those obtained in the foregoing experiments.

Properties.—It dissolves in hot water and cold dilute alkali. With ferric chloride a yellow coloration is produced. With diazotised aniline, an alkaline solution of the substance gave a red dye. It was found not to contain any halogen. Hence the conclusion is that the substance is a phenol, whose probable constitution is 5-nitro-2-acetylamino-3-hydroxytoluene.

2-Propionylaminobenzoic Acid.—This was prepared by heating 2-aminobenzoic acid (10 g.) and propionyl chloride (30 g.) in pyridine solution on a water-bath for 3 hours. The whole was then poured into water, when a brown oil separated which solidified on cooling and scratching. After several crystallisations from rectified spirit it melted at 120-21°. (Found: N, 8.04. $C_{10}H_{11}O_3N$ requires N, 7.23 per cent.).

5-Nitro-2-propionylaminobenzoic Acid.—The nitration of 2-propionylaminobenzoic acid was carried out by dissolving the substance in a mixture of sulphuric acid and acetic acid with good cooling. The raw nitration product first separated as a yellow oil which solidified after sometime and was purified by crystallising it (twice) from dilute alcohol in pale yellow needles, m.p. 199-200°. (Found: N, 11.8. $C_{10}H_{10}O_5N_2$ requires N, 12.24 per cent.).

2-isoButyrylamino-2-aminobenzoic Acid.—2-Aminobenzoic acid (12 g.) was added to benzene (about 100 c.c.) and treated with isobutyryl chloride (crude, 16 g.); the mixture was heated under reflux for six hours, till the acid had gone into solution and evolution of hydrochloric acid had almost ceased. Excess of benzene was then distilled off and the residue—a brown viscous mass—was left in vacuum overnight. The pasty solid thus obtained was dried on a porous plate, dissolved in benzene, boiled with animal charcoal and precipitated with the addition of benzene (twice) as white plates, m.p. 129-30°. (yield 10 g.). (Found: N, 7.3. $C_{11}H_{13}O_3N$ requires N, 6.78 per cent.).

Benzyl 5-Nitro-2-acetylamino-2-aminobenzoate.—5-Nitro-2-acetylamino-2-aminobenzoic acid (2 g.) was dissolved in acetone and treated with moist silver oxide. The precipitated silver salt was filtered off, washed with water and dried in *vacuo*. The dry mass was suspended in benzene, benzyl chloride (2 c.c.) was added and heated under

reflux for 6 hours. A yellowish-white solid was found to have separated, which was filtered off and found to be silver chloride. The benzene filtrate was evaporated when a yellow oil was left which solidified immediately. This was washed several times with alcohol, and then recrystallised from the same solvent in glistening white needles, m.p. 175-76°. (Found: N, 9.17. $C_{10}H_{10}O_5N_2$ requires N, 8.92 per cent.).

Benzyl 5-Nitro-2-propionylaminobenzoate.—This was prepared from the silver salt of 5-nitro-2-propionylaminobenzoic acid and benzyl chloride. The only difference being that the silver salt was prepared by adding silver nitrate to sodium 5-nitro-2-propionylaminobenzoate in water solution. The crude product was twice crystallised from alcohol, in pale yellow needles, m.p. 122-23°. (Found: N, 8.5. $C_{17}H_{16}O_5N_2$ requires N, 8.53 per cent.).

Benzyl 5-Nitro-2-isobutyrylaminobenzoate.—*iso*Butrylaminobenzoic acid (14 g.) was nitrated in sulphuric acid solution, with cooling in ice, with the required quantity of nitric acid (d 1.4). After the operation, the acid solution was poured into crushed ice, when a thick yellow oil separated. The water containing the greater part of acid, was decanted off and washed with fresh ice-cold water several times and allowed to stand overnight. The oil was thus converted into a yellow solid. But further purification of this was not attempted.

The raw nitration product was boiled with water and dilute sodium carbonate solution was added in small quantities at a time, till the brown oil which was formed on heating, had gone into solution. Excess of alkali was then destroyed by the addition of dilute nitric acid and filtered. The clear yellow filtrate was treated with silver nitrate when a yellowish solid separated. This was filtered off and dried in *vacuo* over sulphuric acid. The dry powder was suspended in benzene and converted into the benzyl ester as described before. The crude product obtained after evaporation of benzene, was dried on a porous plate and then crystallised from alcohol in long yellowish needles, m.p. 129-30°. (Found: N, 8.2. $C_{18}H_{18}O_5N_2$ requires N, 8.2 per cent.).

Benzyl 5-Amino-2-acetylaminobenzoate.—The reduction of the corresponding nitro-body was conducted in moist benzene solution with aluminium—mercury couple as described in a previous paper (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 7, 575). The benzene solution, after being left overnight, was found to give green fluorescence. The

separated aluminium hydroxide was filtered off, the liquid dried over fused calcium chloride, filtered and treated with dry hydrochloric acid. The hydrochloride separated as a gelatinous mass. Dry ether was then added and left overnight. The faint pink precipitate was filtered off and dried in *vacuo*. It was dissolved in a mixture of chloroform and alcohol and precipitated with benzene, m.p. 219-20° (decomp). (Found: N, 9.04. $C_{16}H_{17}O_3N_2Cl$ requires N, 8.72 per cent.).

Benzyl 5-Amino-2-propionylaminobenzoate.—The reduction was carried out in ether solution with Al-Hg couple. The hydrochloride of the base was precipitated from the ether solution which dissolved in chloroform with a few drops of alcohol and precipitated with benzene; m.p. 187-88° (decomp). (Found: N, 8.24. $C_{17}H_{19}O_3N_2Cl$ requires N, 8.35 per cent.).

Benzyl 5-Amino-2-isobutyrylamino-2-aminobenzoate.—The nitro-compound was reduced as described before. The hydrochloride was crystallised by dissolving it in chloroform (with a drop or two of alcohol) and petroleum ether; m.p. 207-8° (decomp.). (Found: N, 7.95. $C_{18}H_{21}O_3N_2Cl$ requires N, 8.05 per cent.).

Benzyl Benzoate 2-Acetylamino-5-stibinate of Sodium

The required compound was prepared from benzyl 5-amino-2-acetylamino-2-aminobenzoate, as described in previous communication. The sodium salt (light brown amorphous mass) was purified by dissolving in methyl alcohol and precipitating with ether as a faint pink mass. (Found: Sb, 26.4. $C_{16}H_{15}O_6NSbNa$ requires Sb, 26.08 per cent.).

Benzyl Benzoate 2-Propionylamino-5-stibinate of Sodium.—(Found: Sb, 24.8. $C_{17}H_{17}O_6NSbNa$ requires Sb, 25.3 per cent.).

Benzyl Benzoate 2-isoButyrylamino-5-stibinate of Sodium.—(Found: Sb, 26.1. $C_{18}H_{19}O_6NSbNa$ requires Sb, 25.5 per cent.).

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